

The reaction rate for the substitution of cis-Pt(NH₃)₂Cl₂ by oxalate is found to be almost pH independent throughout the pH range 3 to 9 indicating C₂O₄²⁻ and HC₂O₄⁻ have similar reactivities which agrees with the observations by Teggins, Lee, Baker and Smith⁵.

In four sets of experiments at 35° in which the initial molar concentration ratio of cis-Pt(NH₃)₂Cl₂ and oxalate ranged from 1 : 10 to 1 : 40, values for the rate constants of 4.8-5.4 × 10⁻⁵ sec⁻¹, av. 5.1 × 10⁻⁵ sec⁻¹ were obtained. The established values of the first-order rate constant k = 5.1 × 10⁻⁵ sec⁻¹ at 35°, the enthalpy of activation ΔH* = 18.2 KCal/mole and the entropy of activation ΔS* = -18.9 e.u. may be compared with the corresponding values reported for the first acid hydrolysis of this complex by Reishus and Martin⁴ (e. g., k = 7.6 × 10⁻⁵ sec⁻¹ at 35° ΔH* = 19.7 KCal/mole and ΔS* = -14.0 e.u.). But the value of k = 22.6 × 10⁻⁵ sec⁻¹ at 50° for the cis-Pt(NH₃)₂Cl₂-oxalate reaction is in rather poor agreement with the values of 39.0 × 10⁻⁵ sec⁻¹ at 50° for the same reaction reported by Teggins, Lee, Baker and Smith⁵. However, the value of ΔH* = 18.2 KCal/mole more or less agrees with the activation energy of 17.0 KCal/mole for this reaction reported by them.

It appears that the negative value of ΔS* is caused by electrostriction resulting from the formation of a singly charged three coordinated activated state [Pt(NH₃)₂Cl]⁺ formed by the first order dissociation of [Pt(NH₃)₂Cl₂]⁰. The effect of increasing the ionic strength on the reaction rate is not however pronounced; this might be due to the formation of a neutral ion pair of the type [Pt(NH₃)₂Cl]⁺X⁻, (X⁻ = Cl⁻, HC₂O₄⁻) in the activated state.

The rate of oxalate entry in the complex cis-Pt(NH₃)₂Cl₂ is being studied at present in order to see whether this rate is the same as or different from the chloride release rate. It is expected that this study will reveal the stoichiometric mechanism fully and yield clues as to the intimate mechanism.

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Spectrophotometric Determination of Tantalum (V) by 8-Hydroxy-7-Iodoquinoline-5-Sulphonic acid And Stability Constant of the Complex.

YOGENDU SHARMA & G. C. SHIVAHARE

Chemical Laboratories, Rajasthan University, Jaipur-302004

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8-Hydroxy-7-Iodoquinoline-5-sulphonic acid (Ferron) was used for the determination of tantalum(V) and stability constant of the Tantalum(V)-Ferron complex, by spectrophotometric studies. The effect of

diverse ions has been investigated. The method developed is rapid, sensitive and convenient since this complex is not required to be extracted by non-aqueous solvents.

Experimental

Beckman DU spectrophotometer with optically matched quartz cells of 1 cm. path length were used. The pH measurements were made with a pH meter (Toshniwal, India) having single electrode system. Tantalum pentoxide was supplied by B.A.R.C., Bombay and Ferron was a product of B.D.H. (A.R.).

Tantalum pentoxide was fused with potassium bisulphate to a clear melt. After cooling the melt was extracted with 25% solution of citric acid¹.

Results and Discussion

Absorption Spectrum : The complex shows maximum absorbance at 365 nm. Water was used as a reference.

Effect of pH : The effect of pH on the absorbance was studied. The maximum absorbance was noticed at pH 6.5. Hence in all experiments pH 6.5 was used. Dil. ammonia was used for varying the pH¹.

Calibration graph and stability : The Beer's law is obeyed within the concentration range of 100-500 ppm. The absorbance due to the colour system was found to remain constant for 2 days provided no evaporation took place.

Composition of the complex : To determine the molar composition of the complex formed, Job's method of continuous variation⁴ and the mole ratio method^{2,3,5} were employed. In Job's method the maximum in the curve clearly indicates the formation of Ta⁵⁺-Ferron complex in which the metal-ligand ratio is 1 : 2. The mole ratio method was inconclusive but results obtained are in agreement with those obtained by Job's method.

The average value of stability constant, 'K' determined by these methods is K = 6.4465.

ESTIMATION OF TANTALUM(V)

S. No.	Ta ⁵⁺ taken mg.	Ta ⁵⁺ found mg.	Percentage Error
1.	1.900	1.885	-.78
2.	2.5	2.520	+.80
3.	3.1	3.090	-.32
4.	3.5	3.480	-.57
5.	4.5	4.478	-.48

Precision : The average of five determinations with 3.5 mg. of tantalum (V) is 3.480 mg. which varies between 3.44 mg. and 3.52 mg. with 95% confidence limit.

Interference : Nitrate, sulphate, thiocyanate, fluoride, tartarate and oxalate do not interfere. Chloride ion interferes above 100 ppm. Tungsten, titanium, calcium, ammonium do not interfere. Niobium and vanadium do not interfere if present upto 100 and 150 ppm respectively. Mo⁶⁺, Fe³⁺, Cu²⁺, Ba²⁺, Mn²⁺, Co²⁺, Al³⁺, Cr³⁺ and Ni²⁺ interfere seriously.

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Potentiometric Studies on Ternary Complexes of Nickel (II)

VINOD KUMARI, R. C. SHARMA & G. K. CHATURVEDI

Chemical Laboratories, Agra College, Agra

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THE survey of the literature reveals that the stereochemistry¹ of Ni(II)-thiosalicylic acid complex $H[NiL_3].2C_2H_5OH$ (L=thiosalicylic acid) has been discussed. Whereas salicylic acid has very little or no tendency to form chelate with nickel², thiosalicylic acid (TSA) forms 1 : 1 Ni (II)-TSA chelate in the pH range 3-6. In the present communication the results on the potentiometric studies of the ternary systems: Ni(II)-TSA-gly/tiron/en/pn (where gly=glycine, tiron=1,2-dihydroxy-benzene-3, 5-disulfonic acid disodium salt, en=ethylenediamine, pn=1,2-propylenediamine) have been discussed and formation constants ($\log K_{MAB}$), free energies of formation (ΔF°) for the resulting complexes have been calculated.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of Analar BDH or E. Merck grade and en and pn were used as their dihydrochlorides. .025 M TSA solution was prepared in absolute ethanol. The concentrations of ligand solutions were checked by potentiometric titrations and Ni estimated gravimetrically by the usual method. All the titrations were carried out in duplicate at temperature $25^\circ \pm 0.2^\circ$ keeping the total volume of solution (50 ml in 20% ethanol) and ionic strength (0.1 M KNO_3) constant. pH measurements were made with a Philips Precision pH meter (PR 9405 M).

Calculations

pK values of the ligands were calculated by the method of Chebarek and Martell³ (Table 1), formation constants ($\log K_{MAB}$) by the method of Thompson and Loraas⁴ and free energies of formation (ΔF°) by the expression : $\Delta F^\circ = -RT \ln K_{MAB}$ (Table 2).

TABLE 1

Ligands	pK ₁	pK ₂
en	7.05	9.75
pn	6.91	9.78
gly	—	9.79
tiron	7.67	12.48 ^{Ref 5}

TABLE 2

Ternary system	$\log K_{MAB}$	ΔF° (kcal/degree/mole)
Ni(II)-TSA-gly	$5.125 \pm .015$	- 6.97
Ni(II)-TSA-tiron	$7.88 \pm .15$	- 10.71
Ni(II)-TSA-en	$6.09 \pm .05$	- 8.28
Ni(II)-TSA-pn	$3.40 \pm .18$	- 4.62

Results and Discussion

In the curve x representing the titration of 1:1 Ni (II)-TSA, a sharp inflexion at m=2 may be attributed to the formation of a light purple 1:1 chelate which probably disproportionates at a higher pH into 1:2 Ni (II)-TSA complex and metal hydroxide giving a second inflexion at m = 3.

Curves a, b, c, and d represent 1:1:1 Ni(II)-TSA-gly/tiron/en/pn ternary systems respectively. In all these cases 1:1 Ni (II)-TSA chelate is initially formed which is evidenced by (i) a light purple colour of the solution (ii) almost superimposable nature of the curves for the ternary systems with the curve x for the binary Ni(II)-TSA system upto $m \approx 2$. Addition of the secondary ligand, however, takes place afterwards giving an inflexion at $m \approx 4$ (at $m = 3$ in the case of gly).

The formation of mixed ligand complexes in all the systems is further supported by :

- (i) non-appearance of a solid phase and a different colour observed during the titration ;
- (ii) the lowering in pH in comparison to binary systems ; and
- (iii) non-superimposable nature of the theoretical composite curves a', b', c', and d' (drawn by adding horizontal distances of Ni(II)-TSA and free secondary ligand curves) with the corresponding curves a, b, c and d for the mixed ligand systems in the region of ternary complex formation.

From the foregoing discussion it is, therefore, evident that in all these cases ternary complexes are formed and the order of stability in terms of secondary ligand is found to be as tiron > en > gly > pn.

Fig. 1.

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